

Kinetics of Protonation of Dye-Base in Benzene

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The present investigation deals with the kinetic studies of reactions between the carbinol base of crystal violet and nine aromatic acids in benzene at 6.5°, 10°, 15°, 20 and 25°C. The overall rate constant k is constant within experimental error when the concentration of the carbinol base is varied implying that the reaction is strictly of first order with respect to the base. But at fixed carbinol base concentration, the overall rate constant increases with acid concentration and the results are expressible by a two constant equation of the type $k = k_x C - k_\beta C^2$. It is believed that the variation of k/C with C is due to the presence of acid-anion complex (homoconjugate anions) of carboxylic acid in solution. Fairly linear relationships are obtained when the values of $\log k_x$ in benzene for different acids are compared with the corresponding K_a values (equilibrium constant) in benzene and with the pK_a values in water. It is also concluded that the electrical effect of the substituents has got a dominating influence on the acid strength in benzene medium. A good linearity is also obtained when the values of $\log k_x$ are plotted against the Hammett's substituent constant σ . The overall energy of activation lies between 3.7 to 10.2 Kcal/mole. The individual rate constant (k_1 and k_{-1}) for the dye-acid interaction using the known values of the equilibrium constant have been calculated.

The kinetics of acid-base reactions in benzene has been little studied so far, as these reactions are too fast to be studied by usual means. The reaction between the colourless solutions of the carbinol base of crystal violet and the organic acids however takes place at a measurable rate in benzene with the formation of a violet coloured salt ($\lambda_{max} = 610$ nm) according to the equation :

and the colour intensity reaches a constant value at equilibrium. The kinetics of these reactions could therefore be easily followed spectrophotometrically. The present paper reports the results of kinetic studies at different temperatures of nine aromatic acids with the carbinol base of crystal violet in benzene spectrophotometrically.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

The carbinol base of crystal violet was prepared by the extraction technique introduced by Palit^{1,2}. The purification of the solvents and the acids as well as the preparation of the experimental stock solutions of the carbinol base and the acids has been previously described³. The determination of the total concentration of the dye has been done by the

same procedure as described earlier³. The necessary experimental precautions and conditions of equilibrium studies³ were maintained in all kinetic studies

Procedure for Kinetic Experiments : The experimental solutions of both the carbinol base ($2-4 \times 10^{-6}$ mole/l) and the acid (10^{-4} to 10^{-3} mole/l) after cooling to 6.5° in a thermostat were mixed thoroughly noting the mixing time. Next the mixture was quickly transferred into a stoppered silica cell (cooled at 6.5°) which was then immediately placed in the cell compartment thermostated at $6.5^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The spectrophotometric readings were taken at 610 nm usually after two minutes of mixing in a Hilger UV spectrophotometer. Sufficient time (usually 1-2 hr) was allowed before noting down the equilibrium reading. Similar experiments were performed at temperatures 10° , 15° , 20° and 25° . The temperature was controlled within $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

Two sets of kinetic experiments were done. In one case, the carbinol base concentration was varied at fixed acid concentration and in another, the acid concentration was varied at fixed base concentration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Calculation of the Rate Constant : In most of our experiments, the concentration of the acid being very high compared to that of the carbinol base (10^2 to 10^3 times), equation (1) can be regarded as a pseudo-unimolecular reversible reaction whose overall rate constant $k(=k_1+k_{-1})$ should be given by equation (2) :

$$k = (k_1 + k_{-1}) = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{x_e}{x_e - x} \quad \dots (2)$$

where k_1 and k_{-1} are the rate constants for the forward and the reverse reaction respectively, x is the concentration of the coloured salt in terms of optical density at the time interval ' t ' in minutes and x_e is the equilibrium concentration of the coloured salt in the same unit. The overall rate constants ' k ' were evaluated graphically from the slopes obtained by plotting $-\log(x_e - x)$ vs. t .

FIG. 1

Fig.-1. Plots of $-\log(x_e - x)$ vs. time at different concentration of carbinol base in benzene at 15° . Concentration of *m*-Chlorobenzoic acid in all cases is $4.51 \times 10^{-4} M$. Carbinol base concentration $\times 10^6 M$, (1) 3.90; (2) 3.12; (3) 1.95.

When the concentration of the carbinol base of crystal violet is varied and the acid concentration is kept fixed, parallel straight lines are obtained by plotting $-\log(x_e - x)$ vs. time t (Fig. 1) indicating the constancy of the overall rate constant k . The reaction is therefore strictly first order with respect to the base. On the other hand, when $-\log(x_e - x)$ vs. time t is plotted for various concentrations of an acid at a fixed carbinol base concentration, good linear relationship is obtained under all conditions (Fig. 2), but they are no longer parallel to each other. The values of k increase with increase in acid concentration. This fact is more pronounced at higher temperature. Hence, this pseudo unimolecular reaction is higher than first order with respect to the acid. The latter observation is somewhat unexpected and indicates that the carboxylic acid reactant may catalyse the reaction.

FIG 2

Fig.-2. Plots of $-\log(x_e - x)$ vs. time for reaction in benzene at carbinol base concentration $3.94 \times 10^{-6} M$ with different concentrations *m*-Nitrobenzoic acid at 15° . Acid concentration $\times 10^4 M$ —(1) 1.066; (2) 0.948; (3) 0.829; (4) 0.711; (5) 0.592.

Variation of k with Acid Concentration: Since the equilibrium is far to the right of equation (1), k_{-1} is negligible in comparison to k_1 and so $k \approx k_1$. We, therefore, base all our latter discussions on k taking it to be a measure of the protonation power of the acid.

FIG 3

Fig 3. Plots of k/C vs. C for evaluation of k_{ca} , the catalytic constant of *p* Nitrobenzoic acid at different temperatures. (1) 6.5° ; (2) 10° ; (3) 15° ; (4) 20° ; (5) 25° .

Since k is not directly proportional to the catalyst concentration as it is usually the case in catalysed reactions, the ratio k/C has been linearly extrapolated to zero concentration by plotting k/C vs. C (Fig. 3) following the equation,

$$k = k_{\alpha}C - k_{\beta}C^2$$

a procedure followed by Bronsted and Bell⁴ in a similar circumstance. Both k_{α} and k_{β} are constants for each acid and the extrapolated value k_{α} is termed as 'catalytic constant' which can be used for comparison of protonation power of different acids (Table I).

TABLE I

Values of k_{α} at different temperatures and activation energy

Acid	pK_a^{**} in water at 25°C	k_{α} in benzene at various temperatures (°C) (1 mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)					Activation Energy E Kcal/ mole
		6.5°	10.0°	15.0°	20.0°	25.0°	
<i>m</i> -Toluic	4.28	4.58×10	5.96×10	7.21×10	9.51×10	1.14×10^2	7.8
Benzoic	4.17	7.51×10	9.31×10	1.15×10^2	1.41×10^2	1.51×10^2	7.1
<i>m</i> -Methoxybenzoic	4.09	1.09×10^2	1.26×10^2	1.79×10^2	$2.48 \times 10^2^*$	3.01×10^2	9.5
<i>m</i> -Iodobenzoic	3.85	6.40×10^2	8.35×10^2	1.17×10^3	1.29×10^3	1.45×10^3	6.9
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzoic	3.82	7.60×10^2	9.85×10^2	1.08×10^3	1.41×10^3	1.51×10^3	7.5
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic	3.46	5.30×10^3	5.67×10^3	6.62×10^3	7.08×10^3	7.81×10^3	3.7
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic	3.40	5.18×10^3	6.07×10^3	6.55×10^3	7.01×10^3	8.25×10^3	4.2
Salicylic	3.00	8.70×10^3	1.02×10^4	1.55×10^4	1.95×10^4	2.70×10^4	10.2
<i>o</i> -Bromobenzoic	2.82	2.45×10^2	2.87×10^2	3.57×10^2	4.16×10^2	4.88×10^2	6.3

* In toluene 2.36×10^2

** Values taken from reference 15.

According to Bell^{5,6}, the variation in the catalytic power and hence the protonation power with acid concentration is due to the presence of associated double molecules (dimers) of carboxylic acids. But as shown in our equilibrium studies³, the hyper-acidic nature of organic acids in benzene medium and the cause for the variation in the catalytic power could be better explained due to the presence of the acid-anion complex rather than by the simple associated double molecules.

The relation between Acid Strength and Protonation Power : Values of k_{α} at different temperatures are summarised in Table-I. The following features are noticed :

(i) The value of k_{α} seems to be almost independent of the solvent (benzene and toluene).

(ii) On plotting $\log k_{\alpha}$ against pK_a in water (Fig. 5), a fairly good linear relationship is obtained. The only serious departure is shown by *o*-bromobenzoic acid, which may be due to the so called ortho-effect, because intramolecular hydrogen bonding has been shown to be absent by IR studies^{7,8}. Furthermore, since pK_a values in water are already known³

to be linear with $\log K_a$ values where K_a is the equilibrium constant of the same protonation reaction in benzene, it is expected that $\log k_a$ will be linear with $\log K_a$ which has been found to be the case (Fig. 4). It is to be noticed that the slope of the latter curve is less than

FIG 4

Fig.-4. Plot of $\log k_a$ vs. $\log K_a$ (benzene) at 25° showing the relation between acidic strength and catalytic power of various acids. (1) *m*-Chlorobenzoic, (2) *p*-Nitrobenzoic; (3) *m*-Toluic; (4) *m*-Nitrobenzoic; (5) Benzoic; (6) Salicylic acid.

unity, which points out that these two quantities are related by a Bronsted type relation, $k_a = (\text{constant})K_a^\alpha$. This linearity of rate-equilibrium relation implies that the reactions between the different organic acids and the carbinol base of crystal violet proceed by a similar interaction mechanism.

FIG 5

Fig.-5. Plot of $\log k_a$ vs. pK_a in water at 25° showing the relation between acidic strength and catalytic power of various acids. (1) *m*-Toluic; (2) *m*-Methoxybenzoic; (3) *m*-Iodobenzoic; (4) *m*-Chlorobenzoic; (5) *m*-Nitrobenzoic; (6) *p*-Nitrobenzoic; (7) Benzoic; (8) Salicylic and (9) *o*-Bromobenzoic acid.

(iii) Table-I shows that for monosubstituted benzoic acids the values of k_a follow the order : $o\text{-OH} > m\text{-NO}_2 > p\text{-NO}_2 > m\text{-Cl} > m\text{-I} > o\text{-Br} > m\text{-OCH}_3 > \text{H} > m\text{-CH}_3$. The order of relative strengths of the meta-substituted acids in benzene (in terms of their k_a values)

are in complete agreement with the order of the electron attracting character of the substituents viz., $\text{NO}_2 > \text{Cl} > \text{Br} > \text{I} > \text{OCH}_3 > \text{H} > \text{CH}_3$. Exactly similar observation has been made by Davis *et al.*⁹ in their work on the equilibrium interaction of bromophthalein magenta *E* with organic acids in benzene. Therefore, it can be concluded that the electrical effect of the substituents is the dominating influence on the acid strength in aprotic solvents.

Effect of Substituents: In order to see the effect of substitution on the rate of our acid-base reaction and hence on the protonation power of different organic acids, we tested the Hammett's equation¹⁰.

$$\log k - \log k_0 = \rho\sigma$$

where k is the rate constant for a compound with a meta or para substituent, k_0 is the corresponding constant for the parent (unsubstituted) compound, ρ is the reaction constant and σ is the substituent constant.

Plots of $\log k_a$ values at different temperatures from 6.5° to 25° (instead of the overall rate constants which are dependent on acid concentration in our case) against the standard σ values at 25° give good straight lines for all acids studied except for *p*-nitrobenzoic acid (Fig. 6). Thus, it is concluded that our rate data are consistent with the Hammett equation.

FIG. 6.

Fig.-6. Plot of $\log k_a$ against Hammett's substituent constant σ at different temperatures—(1) *m*-toluic; (2) *m*-Methoxybenzoic; (3) *m*-Iodobenzoic; (4) *m*-Chlorobenzoic; (5) *m*-Nitro benzoic and (6) *p*-Nitrobenzoic acid.

Evaluation of ρ at 6.5° from Fig. 6 gives a value of 2.66. Since it is known that for the ionisation of benzoic acids in water at 25° ρ is equal to +1.0, a greater value of ρ in our case i.e., 2.66 indicates a reaction which is more sensitive to the electrical effect of the substituents than is the former reaction. Figure 6 also points out that ρ decreases with temperature.

Effect of temperature: The kinetic studies at different temperatures indicate the usual increase of rate with temperature. The sensitivity of the rate constant k to the concentration of acid is observed to become less and less pronounced as the temperature is lowered in the case of benzoic, *m*-methoxy and *m*-toluic acid.

The overall energies of activation (Table-I) were calculated by plotting $\log k_x$ against $1/T$, a procedure followed by Bell⁵ in a similar study of acid-base catalysis. The values of the overall activation energies follow the order: salicylic > *m*-methoxy > *m*-toluic > *m*-chlorobenzoic > *m*-nitrobenzoic acids. The energies of activation for proton transfer reactions^{11,12,13} at very low temperature (-78° to -20°) in non-aqueous solutions like alcohol or alcohol-toluene mixture has been found to be 8.5 to 13.6 Kcal/mole. The energies of activation obtained for our acid-base systems, viz., 3.7 to 10.2 Kcal/mole, are lower than the above reported values. The reason may be attributed to the hydrocarbon medium used in our case.

The Individual Rate Constants: Palit and Bhowmik¹⁴ have suggested in a similar study that the equilibrium where both the forward and the reverse reactions are assumed to be influenced by the acid can be formulated in the following way:

where f and r are the acid exponents for the forward and the reverse reaction respectively and the overall acid exponent ' n ' is equal to $(f-r)$, $K_a (= k_1/k_{-1})$ is the equilibrium constant and $k (= k_1+k_{-1})$ is the overall rate constant. From the above consideration the following equation is easily deduced:

$$\frac{k}{K_a + (\text{Acid})^{-n}} = k_{-1}(\text{Acid})^f$$

or

$$\log \frac{k}{K_a + (\text{Acid})^{-n}} = \log k_{-1} + f \log (\text{Acid}) \quad \dots (4)$$

It is evident from the above equation (4) that a plot of $\log[k/K_a + (\text{Acid})^{-n}]$ against $\log (\text{Acid})$ will give a straight line with slope equal to ' f ' and intercept equal to $\log k_{-1}$. All the four kinetic constants k_1 , k_{-1} , f and r can, therefore, be evaluated.

It is seen from Fig. 7 that when $\log[k/K_a + (\text{Acid})^{-n}]$ is plotted against $\log (\text{Acid})$, good

Fig. 7. Plots of $\log [k/K_a + (\text{HA})^{-n}]$ vs $\log (\text{HA})$ for evaluation of individual rate constants and acid exponents. (1) *p*-Nitrobenzoic and (2) *m*-Nitrobenzoic acid.

linear plots are obtained for all the acids from which the individual rate constants have been evaluated and the results are summarised in Table-II. It is already known from the values

TABLE II
Summary of the Individual Rate Constants and Acid Exponents at 25°

Acid	Equilibrium ⁺ constant $\log K_a$ at 25°C	$\log k_1$	$\log k_{-1}$	n^+	f	r
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic	8.49	7.19	-1.30	2.150	1.973	-0.177
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic	9.07	6.41	-2.66	2.253	1.774	-0.479
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzoic	7.00	5.15	-1.51	2.193	1.833	-0.360
<i>m</i> -Toluic	4.72	2.81	-1.91	2.412	1.750	-0.662
Benzoic	4.65	3.57	-1.08	2.169	1.875	-0.294
Salicylic	8.93	7.42	-1.85	2.061	1.875	-0.186

+ Values taken from reference 3.

of K_a^3 that $k_1 \gg k_{-1}$. The interesting feature is that ' r ' comes out to be negative, i.e. the acid retards the reverse reaction of equation (3). This can be simply interpreted as due to the complex formation between the coloured dye salt and the acid which is in large excess. If the protonation is done by the monomeric acid alone and if the acid exists almost wholly in the dimeric form, the exponent ' f ' should be $\frac{1}{2}$. The observed value of ' f ' is always higher and probably is a measure of the departure from the above conditions.

Two interesting features emerge from the values of k_1 . Firstly, a plot of $\log k_1$ with pK_a in water gives a fairly linear correlation. Secondly, $\log k_1$ for the four aromatic acids is in the order: *p*-nitrobenzoic acid > *m*-nitrobenzoic acid > *m*-chlorobenzoic acid > *m*-toluic acid, which is also the order of Hammett's σ constant for these substituents and a plot of $\log k_1$ against σ results in a fairly good straight line.

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